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UNDERSTANDING FERTILITY PATTERN AND ITS DETERMINANTS

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Abstract

Fertility may be defined as the reproductive performance measured by actual number of births of an individual a couple or a group of population. Fertility must not be confused with fecundity which may normally be defined as the physiological capacity of a men women or couple, to reproduce live births. Fertility is statistical concept with social relevance, whereas fecundity is a logical concept.

Fertility indicates the actual level of reproductive performance determined by social, cultural, Psychological as well as economic factors. These terms are used quite loosely in medical literature and are sometimes treated as being synonymous (United Nations,1958, p-38).

Fertility measures the rate at which a population adds to itself by births. These measurements may be related to something for example, the total population of the country / total population of the women in the country / region, total women of the child bearing age, total married women etc. If fertility is measured with respect to married couple, we will be ignoring births given by unmarried mothers or widows or births which resulted from pregnancies

The crude birth rate provides a first approximation in any study of fertility and has the advantage of bringing out exact date at which the population increases through births but the major drawback, of such an index is that it uses the total population as denominator though the entire population is never involved in the process of reproduction (Clarke, 1981, p-35). However this measure of fertility is very common particularly in developing countries.

Child woman ratio is a useful index of fertility as it takes into account only females in the reproductive age group. However it also suffers from certain drawback. First, it cannot be tabulated for a year other census years because age distribution data are available for census years only second, it includes only the surviving children below five years of age and not all the children who were actually born. Third it takes into account all females in 15-44 years age groups irrespective of their marital status.

The general fertility rate is the number of the live births in a year born per mile women of normal reproductive age group. It is a definite improvement over crude birth rate as it takes into account only the female population of reproductive age group but it is not an effective refinement for two reasons. Firstly it is related to all the women in child - bearing age group irrespective of marital status and secondly the Fecundity of women is not same during the entire span of child bearing period. It may be pointed out the child bearing rate is appreciably higher in 20-29 age group than in 15-19 and 30-44 age groups.

Age specific fertility rate is the average occurrence of live births to the females of a specific age group per mile women in that particular age group. The total fertility rate is another age sex adjusted measure of fertility which has been regarded as the most sensitive and the most meaningful cross-sectional measure of fertility. It may be defined as the average number of children that would be born alive to a woman (or group of woman) during her life time if during her child bearing years she were to bear children at such age in accord with prevailing age specific fertility rate.

Gross reproduction rate represents the average number of daughters, which ignoring mortality replaces their mothers assuming that the age and sex specific fertility rates for the current period were to continue indefinitely (Woods, 1979, p-96).

It is therefore a measure if the average number of daughter produced by the woman during her female babies born per mile of female population in reproductive age group.

Besides these there are some other measures of fertility some of them are, cumulative fertility rate, and net reproduction rate completed fertility rate and cohort fertility.

Determinants of Fertility:

The number of births occurring in a year in any population is determined partly by demographic factors such as age and sex distribution. The number of married couples their duration of marriage etc. The fertility is also related with other factors of social and economic set up, such as housing conditions, education, income, religion and attitudes towards family size. The determinants may be studied under mainly six broad categories of biological, physiological, demographic, social, economic and political determinants (Chandna, 1992, p-89).

Biological Determinants:

Biologically speaking, race has been found to be the basic factors generation fertility difference (Chandna, 1992 p-90). In New Zealand, for example, Maori fertility is much higher than that at whites, and similarly the fertility of the indigenous population of Rhodesia and Zambia is almost twice than that of the Europeans. New far these differences in their fertility are related with their social differences is not very easy to establish because not all the social groups living in similar environment may be at the same stages.

Another biological factor supposed to effect the fertility of a population is health. Although it is very difficult to establish a direct correlation between the health of an individual and his fertility potential, yet there is no denying the fact that bad hygienic conditions can lead to partial or complete sterility (Clarke, 1981, p-117). Furthermore, normally one would expect that those enjoying good physical and mental health would be more prolific, but more empirical observation show contrary, results as the most under nourished in the world are the most fertile (Chandna 1980, p-74). General health conditions have also an indirect impact upon fertility pattern of the area. Poor health conditions resulting in high incidence of mortality compel the people to go in for large families so that each couple can have at least two three survivors. However, with the improvement in the general health conditions, the mortality rate goes down and people start adopting small families.

Abstinence Determinants:

Fertility is affected by post-partum abstinence. After the birth of a child, the woman is generally sterile for some periods, as the menstrual cycle is not resumed, or it is re-established,

the earlier cycles are involuntary. During this period the possibility of the assurance of conception is very rare, and hence this period of temporary sterility is known as the post partum sterile period. It has been reported in many Indian studies that, as a result of breast feeding, the post-partum amenorrhoea period are longer for Indian women than for American and European women (Chandra Sckarcen, 1961, p-5).

Fertility is also affected by the restrictions imposed by society of otherwise on reunion or sexual exposure of husband and wife, after the birth of a child. Obviously when this period is long, fertility will be less, when the period is short, husband and wife will get opportunity to meet and chances of fertility are bright and more (Raj Hons, 1984, p-71).

Another physiological constraint on unrestricted fertility is the extent of foetal wastage that is still births which varies from country to country and from place to place such information usually collected through sample interview surveys suffers from under reporting (Bhende, 1988, p-213). The physiological factors responsible for the relatively lower fertility in India include adolescent sterility and longer sterile periods between two births flowing from the practice of breast feeding the child for a longer duration. The impact of social customs on the physiological factors affecting fertility also needs to be taken into account.

Demographic Determinants:

Age, structure, sex, composition, residence or urbanization and child mortality are the chief demographic determinants of fertility. The age structure of the population is the basic demographic factor of human fertility because the proportion of population in reproductive age group has a direct bearing upon birth rate, comparisons of birth rates and fertility rates show the importance of age structure, Japan's birth rate in 1962 was 17.2 per thousand and similar to that of Norway, which had 17.3 but really her fertility rates (5.1 per hundred) was much lower than that of Norway (6.37) because her age structure was more youthful (Clarke, 1931, p-117).

The second demographic determinant affecting the fertility of a population is its sex composition. A balance sex ratio would waste normal conditions for average birth rates. The impact of sex as a determinant of fertility can be well judged when we the birth rates of population having sex structure differentials. For example, in India, the urban centers which

largely impact mall in migrants and thus suffer from great paucity of females have low birth rates.

Another demographic determinant leading to the fertility differential is the determinant of residence or degree of organization. Rural fertility exceeds urban fertility in both developed and developing countries. A survey which was conducted in India in 1979 reported that, rural fertility was higher than the urban fertility. It is because of the fact that in the cities there is high cost of living, which the family with a big size cannot afford; concurrently the couples go on for small families. Child mortality is another factor which influences fertility. In the past rate of child mortality was very high. It used to be almost sure and certain that at least one or two children will die. Accordingly the fertility was high so that a cushion was provided for the children who would die at some later stage. Today society has controlled many diseases which used to kill children and no longer show their total strength. Accordingly parents now wish to have only as many numbers of children as they wish to have. This has considerably influenced fertility.

Social Determinants:

Religion, literary, education, age at marriage, breast feeding, status of women, desire of son, polygamy, widowhood and contraceptive methods etc. are main social determinants of fertility.

Religion is considered to be an important factor affecting fertility (Bhende, 1988, p-213). Religion constitutes one of the most important cultural contexts that govern the behavior of its adherents. Affiliations to a particular religious group not only affect day to day behavior and attitudes but it also affects reproductive behavior (Singh, 1988, p-18). Among all the religions, Islam has been found to exercise greatest control over deliberate attempts to check population growth.

Kings lay Davis observed that in India, although the Muslims and the Hindus live in similar environment yet the birth rates of the Muslims were found significantly higher than those of Hindus (Clarke, 1985, p-121). The average number of children born to a Muslim woman is

5.71 as compared to 5.16 to a Hindu female. The differential fertility between two religions is perhaps, mainly due to the fact that the remarriages of widow is allowed in Islam while in Hindu religion it is not. The studies conducted in U.S.A. and Canada have clearly pointed out that the fertility of Roman Catholics has been higher than that of either Protestants or Jews (United Nations, 1973, p-102). Among all religious groups, the Muslims have the highest fertility and the non-catholic Christians the lowest (Gupta, 1994, p-50).

There is a curvilinear relationship between the numbers of children and percentage of females who are literate (Denis, 1951, p-14). A study conducted in Mysore, India revealed that the average number of children born to an illiterate female is 5.5 those who were educated up to high school or more gave birth to only 3.9 children; part of the difference was due to the higher marriage age of those who were educated up to the high school or more. But when the averages were standardized by duration and age at marriage, the difference between the two persisted; although it was smaller the age at marriage is another basic determinant of human fertility goes down when marriage takes place at a late stage. In Europe many people marry at a very late stage and in many more cases the people even do not marry at all. It is well known fact that fertility rate is higher in countries where marriages take place at comparatively early ages. In India marriages take place at very young age, but in West Indies marriages take place at late stage but the boys and girls are permitted to have sex relations and even produce children before marriage. Thus it is not universally correct that fertility will be low, if the marriages take place at late stage, since in India in spite of the fact that marriage takes place at young age but sexual relationship is socially permitted.

Breastfeeding is also under social factor which empowers a woman by allowing her to control her own fertility and enhance her health as well as that of her children (Gopalan, 1995, p-2).

The status granted to the women in the society is also considered to be strong social factor of fertility. Higher fertility in the Islamic world is mostly due to the low status granted to women in society (Clarke, 1985, p-120-121). Among the various socially determinants of fertility the desire to have a son in the family has been quite significant (Chandana 1992, p-94). Although all society on the world considers a family complete of the attainment of a son yet there are certain societies where there is being social or physiological pressure to have a son in

the family due to certain social customs and compulsions (World Bank, 1984). For example, in India in Hindu the Last rites of the deceased parents are traditionally to be performed by the son. Similarly, in the absence of old age homes, the parents in their old age are dependent on their sons because there is a strong social prejudice against the parents living with their daughter. It is in this context, that the desire to have a son has pushed up the Indian fertility rates significantly.

Another social determinant which influences fertility is polygamy (Raj Hons, 1984, p-70). It is a system under which a husband can have more than one wife - this system is not very popular these days.

Widowhood quite obviously influences fertility. It is because without her husband she cannot have legal children but the effect at widowhood on fertility depends on how soon she decides to remarry and at what age she becomes a widow. If a widow decides to remarry immediately then fertility will not be affected, but if she decides to marry at very late stage or not to remarry at all, obviously fertility will be affected (Raj Hons, 1984, p-71).

Several methods of conception control are available today such as Coitus interrupts method, condoms, oral pills, loop and abortion. None of them really satisfies the simple criteria for the ideal birth control method specified by Abraham Stone and Norman E Himes, (Store A and E.N. Himes, 1960, p-69) who state "The Ideal birth control methods should be harmless, reliable and acceptable".

The recent reduction in fertility in India and some other developing countries of the world is to some extent, due to birth control or family planning programmes, an intensive government sponsored family planning programme, growing awareness of the desirability of small families, increasing urbanisation, spread of education and rise in age at marriages are already bringing down the birth rates.

Economic Determinants:

Income and occupation of the couples are the main economic determinants of the fertility. Fertility is generally assumed to be a monotonically decreasing function of income. This may be so because a higher level of income is closely associated with better education, favourable

occupation, and more important a higher and balanced consumption pattern thus reduced mortality. It has been hypothesized that per capita Protein consumption and fertility are inversely correlated and Protein intake is directly related with per capita income.

It may be pointed out that income increase, the total and marginal utility of children as source of security and as production agent decreases, while the direct and indirect cost of rearing of an additional child increases. Hence, higher income and increase in income levels will motivate fertility reduction (Leibenstein, 1963, p-164)

Another most important factor which influences fertility is the occupation of the couple. It is usually seen that those engaged in mental work have less number of children as compared with those who do some sort of physical labour similarly those whose business is such that takes them to clubs and other places of interest and recreation have less number of children. So is the case with the people who are engaged in religious institutions and where both husband and wife are employed on white collar jobs (Raj Hans, 1984,p-76).

Empirical research undertaken in a variety of cultures seems to indicate that the relationship between female employment and fertility behavior depends on the nature of the economic activity engaged in and the setting in which this activity takes place. In addition, the pressure or absence of conflict between mother and worker rates seems to influence the emergence of a fertility employment relationship (Conception, 1974, p-51). It has been found in several studies that the gainfully employed females have a smaller number of children than those who are not employed (Bhede, 1988,p-272). Females began to participate in gainful employment which provided an alternative to child bearing (Bhende, 1988,p-261).

Political determinants:

Each government provides incentives as well as disincentives to check fertility. Facilities are then provided to those who go in for sterilization or similar other measures to check family size (Raj Hans, 1984,p-76).

From the above discussion, it appears that fertility patterns of a population are determined by the combined effects of biological, Physiological, demographic, Social, Economic, and

political determinants. It is not possible to isolate the rate of any single factor because birth rate is the product of all these factors in unison.

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